

Economic determinants of voters' behavior in the 2024 Romanian parliamentary elections

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Abstract

This paper aims to evaluate the link between economic factors and electoral preferences in the 2024 Romanian parliamentary elections. Using the economic voting framework, this study analyses the complex interplay between macroeconomic variables and electoral behavior in legislative elections. Since retrospective, pocketbook, and sociotropic voting are key elements that characterize the Romanian electoral landscape, the study focuses on the links between economic factors and party preferences and incumbent party reelection. Our methodological design enables us to evaluate the real impact of economic variables. Empirical findings suggest that the average net salary and regional economic development are positively related to electoral decisions and reelection of the incumbent party. Unemployment rates are predictors for left-wing parties, and average net salary is more likely to be related with right-wing political parties. The study highlights several limits of economic voting in the 2024 Romanian parliamentary elections, stressing the importance of cultural, historical, and socio-psychological factors in their interplay with economic variables in order to shape electoral decisions.

Keywords

economic voting; parliamentary elections; unemployment rate; regional disparities

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Psycho-sociological dimensions of voting behavior: A brief introduction

Political behavior is an important tool for understanding the quality of national democracy. Together with institutional design, elections, and party systems, political behavior highlights the magnitude of citizens' engagement in political life. Contemporary political theories underscore the role of civic engagement and participation in decision-making. Active citizenship is relevant for understanding the complex relationship between social influence and political power. Political involvement and citizens' actions in the fields of elections, protests, or social movements are related to governmental public policies, political strategies, and civic priorities. Therefore, political behavior is a relevant tool that measures the complex interaction between civic inputs and governmental outputs. For liberal theories of democracy, active political participation is a guarantee of civic rights and political freedom (Beetham, 2004; Diamond, 2003; Dahl, 1971; Bherer et al. 2016; Cohen and Arato, 1994; Hilmer, 2010; Lijphart, 2012).

Participation in public debates, direct involvement in the legislative process, or significant public reactions are signs of a mature and consolidated democratic order. In correlation with this aspect, active political participation shows an increased level of social responsibility. Beyond individuals, aggregate political behavior has a significant role in the field of political decisions and shaping the future of the community. Active participation in public affairs is considered to be an important civic duty because politics shapes everyday life. Moreover, political behavior reflects the level of political legitimacy and the normal functioning of governmental and public institutions. An active and constant civic engagement could reduce political abuse of power, corruption, or clientelism. These political deviations erode social trust in political actors and create premises for vulnerable political systems.

By improving the quality of political representation, voting is an important piece of the political engagement puzzle. It affects who holds the power and the relevance of the legislative process. As part of the modern "social contract", the vote is both a mechanism of accountability and a safeguard of individuals' rights and liberties (Dellavalle, 2021). The first perspective highlights that political leaders have an increased level of responsibility in the field of social, political, and economic decision-making. The second perspective, derived from modern and liberal political philosophy, stressed that the electoral process is an important mechanism to protect liberties by using the principle of governing by consent.

As regards the theoretical perspectives on political behavior, the sociological perspective emphasizes the role played by political socialization in the field of citizens' engagement. In the early 1950s, Lazarsfeld highlighted the impact of social context on the formation of public opinions and behaviors (Lazarsfeld, 1944). Therefore, traditional models of socialization remain important predictors of individuals' beliefs and cognitions. Following this theoretical approach, social opinions and attitudes are "learned" through social interaction. This complex process is based on continuous learning about social facts, political events, and values. Political socialization has three important sequences: political actors, political content, and timing (Hague et.al.1998). Collective or independent political actors have an important role in transferring social or political values, as well as different models of political culture.

The same role is preserved by political institutions that create a fluid channel to transfer political values, to create political identities, and to satisfy individuals' interests or demands. The traditional social environment is involved in shaping attitudes and behaviors through traditional media, family, and other relevant social actors. It creates premises for developing conscious or unconscious

political beliefs as well as implicit or explicit political attitudes. Conversely, a new social environment is characterized by an increased level of digital communication and interaction. The digital landscape could be seen as an ambivalent form of political socialization, illustrating both opportunities and threats for political behavior. New online media are more likely to be related to an increased level of political mobilization and offline participation. Scholars argued that the main advantages of the new digital environment are in the field of political behavior. In addition to this perspective, we aim to stress that online socialization is more likely to be correlated with an increased level of partisanship and isolation. Several academic theories are relevant to understanding how the new digital environment could negatively influence political attitudes and behaviors (Alberto and Zúñiga, 2017; Artieri et.al, 2025; Fuchs, 2023; Gillespie, 2018; Levendusky and Malhotra, 2015; Mellon and Prosser, 2017; Sunstein, 2018). In this respect, “mere exposure effect” (Zajonc, 2001), “selective perceptions” (Festinger, 1957) and “echo chamber” (Barberá, 2020) effects are relevant theoretical directions that capture the complex interplay between political behavior and the new digital landscape (Garrett, 2009; Sievi and Pawelec, 2025).

Concerning the psychological dimension of voting behavior, scholars observed an increased level of correlation between emotions and electoral decisions. Since the 1950s and 1960s, the work of Campbell et al. on *The American Voter* has established political psychology as a relevant paradigm for understanding the link between emotions and decisions in the field of electoral behavior (Campbell et al., 1980). Political psychologists underscored the role of emotions in shaping both political attitudes and behaviors. Cognitive psychology had an important role in explaining the psychological mechanisms behind political choices. Traditional models of political psychology presented the relation between brain and mind in terms of connectionist networks. As a basic paradigm in cognitive and social psychology, social learning theory helps us to understand both how neural networks and the process by which individuals learn about social facts and actions. Recent findings from neurocognitive psychology reflect a strong relationship between brain structure, psychological process, and political attitudes and behaviors. Therefore, most empirical research reveals that political cognition is an ambivalent form of knowledge, based on both emotional and rational responses to political stimuli (Alford and Hibbing, 2004; Amodio et al., 2007; Arcuri et al., 2008).

Economic voting and rational choice. Literature review perspectives

Beyond the sociological and psychological perspectives, the economic theory of political behavior emphasizes the importance of economic variables in shaping participation and voting choices. The foundational ideas of this approach are presented in Downs' influential work, *An Economic Theory of Democracy* (Downs, 1957). Empirical studies have argued the importance of economic voting across different countries or geographical regions. These findings reveal the strong co-integration over time between political and economic variables (Dassonneville and Lewis-Beck, 2019). Citizens are considered rational actors who align their preferences with economic performance and development (Anderson, 2000; Anderson, 1995; Crewe and Denver, 1985; Dassonneville and Lewis-Beck, 2014; De Vries et al., 2018; Duch and Stevenson, 2006; Lewis-Beck, 1988; Lewis-Beck et al. 2008; Lewis-Beck and Paldam, 2000; Pickup and Evans, 2013).

Stability over time and change are two forces that drive electoral decisions. Behavioral inertia, ideological attachment, and partisan loyalty are the core forces of stability. In contrast, dissatisfaction, economic imbalances, and preferences for opposite parties are relevant for understanding the role played by change in electoral dynamics. Behavioral inertia is strongly related to support for the incumbent party. Emotional attachment and cultural values could explain the strong correlation

between partisanship and preferences for the incumbent party. High rates of inflation or unemployment are more likely to be related to preferences for the opposite political parties.

Following these normative premises, our study aims to create the nexus between economic determinants and voting behavior in terms of “reward and punishment”. Economic context explains why several elections preserve the governmental political party or coalition, while other elections are characterized by an increased support for opposition parties (Powell and Whitten, 1993; Fiorina, 1981; Monroe, 1979). Critics of economic voting argued that globalization diminishes the impact of economic factors on voters’ electoral decisions (Anderson, 2007; Paldam and Nannestad, 2000; Bartels, 1996). The international context is more important than national or regional factors in shaping political beliefs or behaviors (Rudolph, 2003). The diffusion of economic responsibility across different institutions, the European economic market, and global economic trends has likely weakened the magnitude of the economic vote. The decline of the traditional cleavages, such as urban/ rural divisions, religious affiliation, and partisan loyalties, has led to the emergence of economic voting as a strong mechanism through which citizens assess governmental performance. As rational evaluators of governmental performance, citizens can “reward” or “punish” the governmental party using economic criteria. In this respect, an important part of the academic literature argued that economic voting has remained consistent over time, unaffected by significant structural challenges. Empirical findings suggest that, on a long-term analysis, economic votes remain an important part of the political behavior. Therefore, there is a significant and stable relationship between economic performance and electoral outcomes across decades.

The magnitude of the relationship is explained by national contexts and countries’ historical legacies. These findings demonstrated that economic voting is a constant and reliable feature of democratic participatory behavior. Also, these important findings demonstrate the rational choice hypothesis in different political and historical contexts. Despite the institutional design and challenges of the structural dynamics, the economic situation remains an important criterion for individuals’ assessment of governmental performance. National contexts and cultures are relevant mediators in the correlation between economic performance and people’s choices. This type of economic vote is strongly related to retrospective evaluations. Thus, retrospective voting is an important piece of the puzzle in a context dominated by political polarization, ideological hybridization, and media influence. In contrast with other factors, economic variables indicate the importance of the governmental outcomes for citizens. An increased level of economic development is more likely to be correlated with an increased rate of re-election. Conversely, bad economic times are more likely to be related to electoral preferences for opposite political parties. Incumbent re-elections depend on the economic results and civic positive evaluations to “reward” the ruling party.

Economic vote is based on the “responsibility hypothesis”, suggesting that voters are more likely to “reward” or “punish” when they can identify which political actors are responsible for economic outcomes (Duch and Falcó-Gimeno, 2021; Angelova et al., 2016). Instead of this, it is very difficult to evaluate economic outcomes when the governmental structure is based on political coalitions. In coalition systems, scholars observed a diffuse and weak relationship between economic outcomes and electoral decisions (Bäck et al., 2011; Baker et al., 2016; Bawen and Rosenbluth, 2006; Debus et al., 2014; Duch and Stevenson, 2008; Duch and Stevenson, 2013; Hobolt, 2013; Park, 2019). In line with these theoretical aspects, an empirical study conducted by Powell argued that economic voting is conditional (Powell and Whitten, 1993). This is important in single-party governments, or in situations in which it is clear that the party has responsibility for economic decisions. Thus, results confirmed that coalition governments are less likely to be punished for poor economic results. An

important conditionality derives from political ideology. Results confirmed that right-wing governments are more prone to be punished for inflation. Conversely, left-wing governments are punished for unemployment. The novelty of this study is represented by the connection between ideological orientation and punishment for economic outcomes (Powell and Whitten, 1993).

Together with ideological orientation, political perception, and information are catalysts of electoral decisions. Scholars emphasized that information is a key mediator variable between institutional design, complexity, and responsibility attribution. Well-informed voters are more inclined to understand how economic and political institutions function. Also, informed citizens can distinguish between political actors and their real impact in the field of economic decisions. Therefore, they can link economic outcomes to a specific political party or leader. Political information enhances democratic accountability. Only informed citizens could avoid media partisanship and evaluate the real social or economic governmental performances (Gomez and Wilson, 2006).

An increased level of political information is related to cognitive complexity or sophistication. Using economic data, scholars have attempted to explain why a consistent portion of the electorate is driven by economic motivations. Their perspectives support the research hypothesis: "economic voting is conditional on political sophistication." Gomez and Wilson developed a new theoretical framework that supports the theory of cognitive heterogeneity (Gomez and Wilson, 2006, pp. 127-145). Scholars argued that citizens' ability to process information is very different, generating significant variations in political perceptions and electoral decisions. Politically sophisticated citizens are more likely to vote based on their personal economic or financial situation. This is a form of pocketbook or egotropic voting. Conversely, citizens concerned with social outcomes are more likely to be correlated with a sociotropic vote. Less informed citizens tend to vote sociotropically, focusing on social or national economic outcomes, rather than personal economic conditions. Individuals' wages and job conditions are relevant predictors of pocketbook voting. Macroeconomic variables such as economic growth, inflation rates, unemployment, or governmental debt are relevant predictors of sociotropic voting. Empirical findings reveal that sociotropic voting is present across all levels of political sophistication. Unlike pocketbook voting, which is supported by personal perceptions and evaluations of personal economic conditions, sociotropic assessments are more intuitive and socially anchored, being accessible to a large number of citizens (Duch, 2001).

An important theoretical direction highlights the relevance of political perceptions in shaping electoral decisions. Thus, voters adjust their electoral preferences based on their perceptions of political performance (Tilley et al. 2008; Tverdova, 2012; Stroud and Lee, 2013). The competence model suggests that the national political context influences political behavior (Anderson, 2007). Statistical validation of this model confirms that an increased level of responsibility concentration is positively related to the economic vote.

Traditional perspectives reveal the impact of economic factors in the field of consolidated democracies. A significant number of empirical studies have demonstrated that economic voting remains an important variable that shapes the voters' behavior in fragile or transitional democracies. In flawed democracies, media partisanship, party system, and institutional arrangements could impact electoral decisions. Together with these systemic and structural factors, economic preferences and perceptions remain key factors in explaining electoral dynamics. Empirical research provided strong evidence regarding the importance of unemployment rates in electoral decisions.

Regarding the situation in post-communist countries, empirical studies revealed an important social division that might affect the dynamics of economic voting: winners and losers of democratic reforms (Lewis-Beck and Stegmaier, 2008). Therefore, voting behavior is shaped by personal

experiences with economic reforms (Fidrmuc, 2000; Harper, 2000). These groups support different political parties due to the impact of economic reforms on their livelihoods. Winners of reforms (entrepreneurs, urban residents, and highly educated citizens) are more likely to vote with reformist and right-wing political parties. Conversely, losers of reforms (rural residents, unemployed, or agricultural workers) tend to vote with left-wing or nationalist political parties. In this context, citizens support parties that might deliver favorable economic policies. Unemployment is an important marker of left-wing preferences. Entrepreneurial activity and increased rates of economic growth are relevant indicators for pro-reformist electoral preferences. In line with these findings, net wages are related to both reformist and left-wing political parties. A decreased level of net wages is strongly related to electoral preferences for left-wing or nationalist political parties. These statistical models highlight that support for the government party is affected by changes in unemployment rates and net salary growth. Swing voters are more likely to respond to economic conditions, revealing the impact of governmental economic responsibility in transitional countries.

The theory of economic voting underlines the importance of political context, cognitive heterogeneity, and democratic evolutions in shaping electoral decisions. In consolidated democracies, economic voting is strongly related to governmental responsibility. Economic performance is an important predictor of the “punishment and reward” mechanism. In transitional democracies, personal experiences and social class membership might predict the dynamics of electoral preferences for left and right-wing political parties. Economic voting depends on political institutions, party system, political information, and historical legacy. Economic messages and subjective perceptions are important factors that mediate the complex interplay between the economy and electoral behavior.

Data collection and research methods

This paper evaluates the relevance of economic voting theory in Romanian Parliamentary elections. Grounded in the theoretical framework of economic voting, our analysis evaluates both incumbency advantage in correlation with economic factors and party-specific electoral dynamics. Beyond political ideologies, economic voting is an important measure of governmental performance. Citizens are more sensitive when economic conditions are unfavorable. Inflation rates, unemployment, net salaries, and economic growth are relevant factors that might predict voting behaviors. Together with these objective economic factors, personal experiences and subjective perceptions are related to both retrospective and prospective voting.

In line with the academic literature on economic voting, this article aims to answer the following research questions: Q1: What is the relationship between regional differences in the economic conditions and electoral preferences? Q2: How have the increased unemployment rates affected the dynamics of electoral preferences for left or right-wing political parties? Q3: To what extent do the county’s economic conditions influence incumbency rates? Q4: What is the impact of the net wage growth on the field of electoral preferences? Q5: To what extent do regional economic disparities influence support for nationalist or reformist political parties?

Aligned with these research questions, our research objectives are: O1: to evaluate the correlation between economic conditions and electoral preferences across Romanian geographical regions; O2: to estimate the magnitude of correlation between unemployment rates and electoral preferences for left or right-wing political parties; O3: to observe the economic factors that might predict incumbency rates in Romanian’s counties; O4: to estimate the correlation between new salary growth and electoral support for different political parties. O5: to identify significant predictors of electoral behavior in the Romanian 2024 Legislative elections. By these research questions and

objectives, we assume the following research hypotheses: H1: An increased level of economic development is positively related to an increased level of electoral support for the incumbent party. H2: Average net salary predicts the increased level of incumbent party reelection. H3: High unemployment rates are positively associated with left-wing party preferences. H4: An increased level of average net salary is positively associated with right-wing party preferences.

By focusing on regional disparities, development level, and key macro-economic variables, the analysis aims to identify patterns of electoral support across counties. To advance these investigations, this section presents the research variables, datasets, and quantitative models used to capture the complex interplay between electoral preferences and economic factors. In this respect, we used secondary statistical data regarding the rates of reelection for the incumbent party, electoral scores, economic indicators, educational level, and spatial distribution of votes by urban/ rural cleavage.

Dependent variables. Consistent with academic literature, the analysis focuses on incumbency rates and party-level electoral scores from the 2024 Romanian Legislative Elections. The incumbent refers to the political party that controls the government at the time of elections. In the Romanian electoral system, the incumbent party means the party or coalition that has formed the government and holds the majority in Parliament. In connection with academic literature, the incumbent party is punished or rewarded depending on how the economy performs under its leadership. This variable aligns with the responsibility hypothesis, which assumes that voters hold the incumbent accountable for economic conditions. The variable Incumbent Party is used to capture electoral support in the 2024 Romanian Legislative Elections. We used a dummy variable with a value of 1 when the electorate favors the governing party and a value of 0 when voters opt for a different or opposition political party.

Besides the incumbent party, we used the electoral scores obtained by political parties as dependent variables in the 2024 Romanian Legislative elections. We included in the dataset those political parties that officially surpassed the electoral threshold of 5%. Therefore, in our analysis, we used the electoral scores obtained by the following political parties: Social Democratic Party (PSD), National Liberal Party (PNL), Alliance for the Union of Romanians (AUR), Save Romanian Union (USR), Democratic Union of Hungarians in Romania (UDMR), S.O.S. Romania (S.O.S), Party of Young People (POT).

The Social Democratic Party (PSD) is the main center-left political party, with strong support in rural areas and among older people. This party was founded in the early 1990s, as the successor of the National Salvation Front (FSN), and governed the country after the fall of communism. The National Liberal Party (PNL) is a traditional party founded in 1875, being an important promoter of liberal values, and having an important role in political modernization both before and after the communist era. The Alliance for the Union of Romanians (AUR) is a right-wing radical party, promoting nationalist, conservative, and sovereign values. This party was founded in 2019, being an anti-establishment alternative in the Romanian post-communist political context. Emerging from the civic movement Save Bucharest Union, the current party Save Romania Union (USR) is a right-wing political party with pro-European values and orientation. It has a strong anti-corruption rhetoric and reformist approach, having electoral support among urban and highly educated voters.

The Democratic Union of Hungarians in Romania (UDMR) is a centrist political organization representing the Hungarian minority since 1989. It has had a consistent presence in Legislative elections and governance since 1996, promoting a political platform in ethnic advocacy. Following the Alliance for the Union of Romanians (AUR), S.O.S. Romania is a far-right political party founded in 2021, which promotes an anti-establishment rhetoric, strong Euroscepticism, and a traditional approach regarding Romanian sovereignty. The Party of Young People (POT) was founded in 2023 by a former

member of AUR. The party is right-wing populist and sovereignist, having a nationalist and anti-establishment rhetoric. The party surpassed the 5% electoral threshold, securing seats in the 2024 Romanian Parliamentary elections.

Independent Factors. To evaluate the impact of the economic factors on Romanians' electoral behavior, the paper uses the following independent factors: a. unemployment rates by counties; b. average net salary by county; c. gross domestic product by county; d. gross domestic product per inhabitant by county; e. gross value added by county and activities; f. gross domestic product per inhabitant - index of disparity. In connection with the aforementioned economic variables, the research incorporates data related to education and demographic structure. Therefore, the study includes the percentage of individuals with at least upper secondary education and demographic density by county. Table 1 presents the research variables and data sources:

Table 1. Research variables, units of measurement, and sources of data

Variable	Symbol	Measurement Unit	Sources of Data
Incumbency party	INC	0 – Opposition/other party 1 – Incumbent party	https://prezenta.roaep.ro/parlamentare-01122024/pv/romania/results/ (ROAEP)
Electoral scores in 2024 Parliamentary elections (by political party)	ES	% of votes (0-100)	https://prezenta.roaep.ro/parlamentare-01122024/pv/romania/results/ (ROAEP)
Unemployment	UN	0-10	https://insse.ro/cms/ro/tags/comunicat-ocuparea-si-somajul (INS)
Average net salary	ANS	RON/ month	https://insse.ro/cms/ro/tags/comunicat-castig-salarial (INS)
Gross domestic product	GDP	RON/ year	https://insse.ro/cms/en/tags/regional-national-accounts (INS)
Gross domestic product per inhabitant	GDP/ capita	RON/ inhabitant	https://insse.ro/cms/en/tags/regional-national-accounts (INS)
Gross value added by county and activities	GVA	RON/ year	https://insse.ro/cms/en/tags/regional-national-accounts (INS)
Index of disparity	ID	0-100	https://insse.ro/cms/en/tags/regional-national-accounts (INS)
Education	ED	0-100	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/ddn-20221026-1 (EUROSTAT)
Demographic density	DD	0-100	https://www.recensamantromania.ro/rezultate-rpl-2021/rezultate-definitive-caracteristici-demografice/ (INS)

The data set includes relevant political, economic, and demographic indicators for the 2020-2024 electoral cycle, covering 42 counties (including Bucharest). Using these data to capture trends from 2020 to 2024, we aim to observe the economic influences in shaping electoral preferences for the incumbent or other political parties. Following these perspectives, we used a quantitative research design based on both descriptive and inferential statistics. At the descriptive level, the analysis is focused on capturing measures of central tendency, dispersion, and distribution. As regards the inferential statistics, we used two different regression models in order to capture the complex interplay between economy and electoral behavior. The logistic regression is used to estimate the

relevant predictors for the incumbent party. In line with this model, we used multiple linear regression equations to capture the complex relationship between economic, educational, and demographic variables and the electoral scores obtained by the parliamentary parties in the 2024 Romanian Parliament Elections. Starting from these premises, our models are presented as follows. Let $\omega = \frac{p}{1-p}$, the odds ratio of the dependent variable, then: $\ln(\omega) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot x_1 + \beta_2 \cdot x_2 + \dots + \beta_k \cdot x_k + \varepsilon_{1,k}$.

In this equation, ω is the odds ratio of the dependent variable, $X_{1,k}$ are independent variables, and $\varepsilon_{1,k}$ represent unstandardized residuals. In line with this model, we propose the following binary logistic regression to capture the interaction between economic variables and preferences for the incumbent party:

$$\ln(INC) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot UN + \beta_2 \cdot ANS + \beta_3 \cdot GDP + \beta_4 \cdot \frac{GDP}{capita} + \beta_5 \cdot GVA + \beta_6 \cdot ID + \beta_7 \cdot ED + \beta_8 \cdot DD + \varepsilon_{1,8}$$

In order to capture the interplay between independent factors and electoral scores gained by political parties in the 2024 Romanian Legislative elections, we used a multiple linear regression equation as follows. Let be Y a dependent variable, $X_{1,k}$ independent factors, and $\varepsilon_{1,k}$ unstandardized residuals, then the regression equation is: $Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot x_1 + \beta_2 \cdot x_2 + \dots + \beta_k \cdot x_k + \varepsilon_{1,k}$. As regards our research paper, the model of regression is based on the following structure:

$$ES_p = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot UN + \beta_2 \cdot ANS + \beta_3 \cdot GDP + \beta_4 \cdot \frac{GDP}{capita} + \beta_5 \cdot GVA + \beta_6 \cdot ID + \beta_7 \cdot ED + \beta_8 \cdot DD + \varepsilon_{1,8}$$

In this model, ES_p is the electoral score of the party p , β_0 is the intercept, $\beta_{1,k}$ - regression coefficients, and $\varepsilon_{1,8}$ unstandardized residuals. Besides these regression models, we used the T-test for independent samples to observe statistical differences and the magnitude of effects in the field of electoral preferences for the incumbent party. Regional differences were estimated using one-way ANOVA and F-test, with $p < 0.05$. Statistical data were analyzed by JASP 0.95.0 and IBM-SPSS version 29.0. Statistical results are relevant with the significance level $p < 0.05$.

Economic context and incumbency party reelection

This section presents descriptive statistics results, significant differences between research variables, and the binary logistic regression model based on the interplay between incumbency reelection rates and economic variables. The electoral system in Romania for the two chambers of the legislative assembly (Chamber of Deputies and Senate) is based on a closed-list proportional representation across 42 electoral counties. Romania's electoral system allocates Parliamentary seats proportionally, by the d'Hondt method, based on national votes for political parties that surpass the 5% threshold. Romania's parliamentary elections held on 1st December 2024 took place in a polarized social and political landscape, characterized by a significant voter turnout (52.4%). Compared to the previous electoral cycle, the 2024 Parliamentary elections are characterized by the emergence of new political forces and the erosion of the traditional political parties that governed Romania's landscape in the post-communist period.

Empirical findings reveal electoral preferences for both the traditional PSD and the new nationalist and populist force, AUR. PSD obtained an average electoral score of 24.53% with a standard deviation of 9.77%. As regards the electoral score gained by AUR, results indicate an average score of 18.46 % with a standard deviation of 3.57%. Decreased levels of standard deviation suggest a uniform distribution of the electoral scores across all geographical regions, underlying the prevalence of electoral preferences for this party in regions or counties characterized by economic issues. The liberal

and pro-European forces, represented by PNL and USR, are characterized by asymmetric vote distributions, with high support in urban developed regions and significantly lower scores in rural or peripheral areas. Statistical values indicate an average support for PNL of 14.94% with a standard deviation of 5.63%. In line with this result, USR registered an average electoral score of 10.03% with a standard deviation of 4.37%. The data reflect the concentration of electoral preferences in urban areas, characterized by educated and economically active voters. Particularly, this political profile is found in university centers and developed metropolitan areas.

As regards the electoral scores related to ethnical parties, UDMR is considered a regional political actor, with significant impact in counties with a substantial Hungarian population. UDMR obtained an average electoral score of 7.73% with a standard deviation of 19.63%.

Beyond ethnic-based parties, the 2024 Romanian Parliamentary elections are characterized by the rise of nationalist and populist actors such as S.O.S and POT. In this respect, S.O.S has an average electoral score of 7.44% with a standard deviation of 2%. This political party is characterized by support for nationalist values, Euroscepticism, and often adopts an anti-establishment rhetoric. POT has sought to mobilize young people using social media and populist messages, promoting both sovereignism and Euroscepticism. This party obtained an average score of 6.1% with a standard deviation of 1.24%. Both these parties exhibit relatively low standard deviations in their electoral scores, suggesting a consistent level of support in regions or counties where they were very active. Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics results regarding the electoral scores of the main political parties in the 2024 Romanian Parliamentary elections:

Table 2. Electoral scores in the 2024 Romanian parliamentary elections. Descriptive statistics.

	PSD	PNL	USR	AUR	UDMR	SOS	POT
Mean	24.53	14.94	10.03	18.46	7.73	7.44	6.10
Median	23.95	13.43	8.61	18.30	0.00	6.62	5.75
Std. Deviation	9.77	5.63	4.37	3.57	19.63	2.00	1.24
Skewness	0.06	1.87	1.42	-0.22	3.09	0.68	1.28
Kurtosis	-0.40	4.38	1.52	0.21	9.50	-1.14	1.32
Range	40.43	26.74	18.07	16.11	88.00	5.41	4.19
Minimum	3.00	7.99	5.18	9.88	0.00	5.12	5.01
Maximum	43.43	34.73	23.25	25.99	88.00	10.53	9.20
25th percentile	17.54	11.51	7.00	16.99	0.00	6.13	5.08
50th percentile	23.95	13.43	8.61	18.30	0.00	6.62	5.75
75th percentile	30.55	17.20	11.38	20.64	0.00	9.21	6.71

The one-way ANOVA results indicate that electoral scores of PSD vary significantly across different geographical regions of the country ($F=4.751$, $p < 0.01$). Highest electoral scores were registered in Oltenia's counties (37.74%). Also, in Muntenia (29.19%), Bucovina (25.08%), and Moldova (25.82%), we estimated increased support for PSD. Conversely, the lowest support for social democracy is registered in Transylvania (16.27%), Crișana (14.42%), and Maramureș (17.04%). Banat obtained within 2024 Parliamentary elections an average electoral score of 23.86%. Unlike PSD, the

other political parties analyzed didn't exhibit significant differences in the electoral scores by geographical regions ($F < 2.12$, $p > 0.05$). As regards the electoral scores related to PNL, Crișana (25.96%) and Transylvania (17.13%) are relevant geographical regions that support the party more strongly than other geographical regions. In connection with this result, increased levels of electoral preferences for USR are found in Bucharest (23.25%), Banat (13.25%), and Transylvania (11.14%). Lowest scores related USR are relevant for several geographical regions such as Maramureș (7.80%), Bucovina (6.07%), and Oltenia (8.05%).

Besides these parties, AUR has experienced a rapid rise in electoral preferences, becoming an influential political actor in the current electoral landscape. The most increased electoral scores are found in counties such as Gorj (25.99%), Suceava (25.26%), and Arad (23.5%). In contrast, counties where AUR has experienced a low level of electoral support are Cluj (14.37%), Sălaj (13.26%), Bucharest (12.18%), Bihor (11.29%), and Satu Mare (9.88%). Bucovina (22.08%), Dobrogea (21.57%), and Oltenia (20.77%) are relevant geographical regions for an increased electoral support related to this political party.

In contrast, the center of the country, especially Transylvania, is characterized by a decreased electoral support for nationalist and sovereignist political actors. In line with these findings, we observed electoral support for S.O.S in 33.33% of the counties, dispersed across different geographical units. Moreover, increased support for this party is registered in Dobrogea (10.47%) and Moldova (8.32%). Therefore, in Dobrogea (6.77%) and Transylvania (6.49%), statistical data indicate electoral preferences for POT. Concerning UDMR, we aim to stress that electoral support for this party is found in the Center and Western part of the country, being strongly related to the ethnical dimension. Following these statistical results, Figure 1 shows the distribution of the electoral scores for the main political parties by geographical region.

Figure 1. Electoral scores of PSD, PNL, USR, and AUR by geographical region.

In connection with electoral preferences, this analysis focuses on the evolution of the economic indicators across different counties during the electoral cycle 2020-2024. In this respect, results indicate an average level of unemployment of 4.14% with a standard deviation of 2.12%. Increased levels of unemployment are observed in regions such as Oltenia (5.89%), Bucovina (5.43%), and Moldova (4.64%). Relevant counties for an increased level of unemployment are Dolj (8.87%), Teleorman (8.87%), Vaslui (8.66%), and Mehedinți (8.41%). In contrast, Cluj (1.44%), Timiș (1.18%), and Bucharest (0.75%) are characterized by low unemployment rates, among the lowest in the country. However, in line with the unemployment rates, statistical results show that the net average salary has an average of 4479 RON with a standard deviation of 567 RON.

Concerning the data related to GDP, GDP/ capita, and GVA, empirical findings indicate that Muntenia, Transylvania, Crișana, and Banat are more likely to have an increased level of economic development. As regards the level of secondary education, statistical tests confirm that there is no significant difference in the percentage of citizens with at least secondary education. Overall, the average value is 82.86% with a standard deviation of 3%. Table 3 shows descriptive statistics results for economic, educational, and demographic factors.

Table 3. Economy, education, and demography. Descriptive statistics.

	UN	ANS	GDP	GDPpc	GVA	ID	ED	DD
Mean	4.14	4479	28944	52716	26.40	83.01	82.86	254.84
Median	3.74	4366	19008	47285	17.37	74.35	83.10	66.39
Std. Deviation	2.12	567	46232	23710	42.17	37.09	3.00	315.92
Skewness	0.62	1.78	5.69	3.54	5.70	3.54	-0.04	1.12
Kurtosis	0.09	3.79	34.86	16.83	34.96	16.80	0.55	-0.78
Range	8.38	2694	300756	146579	274.20	229.27	12.60	735.34
Minimum	0.49	3804	8332	27889	7.89	44.10	75.50	43.15
Maximum	8.87	6498	309088	174468	282.08	273.37	88.10	778.49
25th percentile	2.58	4127	12093	41197	10.97	64.94	81.36	63.56
50th percentile	3.74	4366	19008	47285	17.37	74.35	83.10	66.39
75th percentile	5.35	4642	27318	57258	24.97	90.37	83.50	607.1

When comparing economic performance with electoral preferences, we observed a strong relationship between political continuity and development. Regions with a higher level of development tend to have a greater proportion of localities where the ruling party is reelected. Incumbency advantage is more likely to be correlated with economic development than with other social or cultural factors. Regions with lower development are more likely to be correlated with political turnover. As regards electoral data, we estimated that in 76.19% of the counties, citizens voted for the incumbent political party. In contrast, only in 23.81% of the counties have citizens elected the opposition party or other political actors.

To evaluate the impact of the economic factors on the field of incumbency party, we used the binary logistic regression. Using the Backward conditional method in the binary logistic regression, we obtained significant statistical results with pseudo-R²= 0.524, Chi-square= 18.058, p < 0.01. Table 4 captures the main predictors and logistic regression coefficients.

Table 4. Binary logistic regression. Predictors of Incumbent party reelection.

Variables	β	S.E.	Wald	Sig.
Unemployment	0.316	0.433	0.533	0.465
Average net salary	0.070	0.003	6.687	0.010
GDP	-0.005	0.002	4.784	0.029
Gross Value Added	5.062	2.337	4.692	0.030
GDP per capita	0.005	0.005	0.901	0.342
Index of disparity	-3.049	3.221	0.896	0.344
Education	0.205	0.222	0.858	0.354
Demographic density	0.001	0.002	0.064	0.80
Constant	-27.910	11.147	6.269	0.012
Nagelkerke R ²	0.524			0.001

Quantitative results indicate that an increased level of incumbent party reelection is positively correlated with economic conditions. Therefore, significant predictors of incumbent party reelection are average net salary ($p = 0.010$), GDP by county ($p = 0.029$), and gross value added by county and activities ($p = 0.030$). Average net salary and gross value added by county and activities are related positively to an increased level of incumbent party reelection. Higher average net salaries are relevant variables for explaining living conditions and reducing protest voting. Personal finances related to pocketbook voting are relevant tools for understanding the complex mechanism of crystallizing electoral decisions. In line with this argument, gross value added by county and activities measures the value of goods and services produced locally. An increased level of gross value added by activities is a significant predictor of strong regional economies and visible development. In this regard, these findings are relevant for explaining status quo bias and incumbency advantage. Another important economic predictor is represented by the level of GDP. We estimated a negative correlation between GDP and incumbent party advantage. Regional disparities and growth without inclusion are several factors that might mediate the complex interplay between economic development and electoral behavior. In connection with these findings, the equation that describes the complex interplay between incumbent party reelection and economic variables is:

$$\ln(INC) = -27.91 + 0.07 \cdot ANS - 0.005 \cdot GDP + 5.062 \cdot GVA$$

Our statistical model reveals that economic factors are moderately involved in electoral decisions. Retrospective voting based on an individual's economic perceptions and ability to analyze governmental strategies is relevant. The results confirm the hypothesis of retrospective voting, indicating that electoral preferences are affected by the level of regional development, diversity of economic activities or services, and average net salaries. We observed a hybrid voting model in the Romanian electoral landscape, reflecting both elements of pocketbook voting and sociotropic perspectives. Personal finances, as indicated by average net salaries, serve as a significant indicator of egotropic or pocketbook voting. Alternatively, economic development measured by GDP and GVA is a strong marker of sociotropic voting. Consistent with theoretical perspectives regarding economic voting in transitional democracies, our findings in the Romanian electoral landscape indicate a significant correlation between the level of net salary and electoral cognitions, attitudes, and behaviors.

Modelling party choice through economic indicators

This section aims to establish the link between macroeconomic indicators and party preferences in the 2024 Romanian parliamentary elections. If incumbency advantage is positively related to economic performance, in this part of the paper, we aim to identify economic and socio-demographic predictors of party preferences. Several theoretical frameworks can explain the complex interaction between the economy, education, and social or demographic variables. The theory of retrospective voting underscores the importance of economic performance as a mechanism for “reward and punishment”. Good economic times are strongly related to an increased electoral support for the ruling party. Alternatively, economic downturns or crises are associated with a rise in support for opposition or emergent political forces. The theoretical model of personal economic interest suggests the main role played by the cognitive style in electoral decisions. Informed and sophisticated citizens are more prone to elect political parties that align with their personal perceptions, expectations, and current economic situation. In this respect, the model of egotropic vs. sociotropic voting is relevant to understanding social and economic cleavages. In connection with these normative perspectives, the theory of social cleavages explains the complex interaction between social, economic, and cultural variables as predictors of voting behavior.

Table 5. Multiple linear regressions on electoral scores in 2024 Romanian parliamentary elections

Party		Const.	UN	ANS	GDP	GVA	GDPpc	ID	ED	DD
PSD	Std.β	14.513	0.497	-0.013	-0.005	-0.006	-0.070	-0.071	0.300	0.263
	p	0.001	0.001	0.926	0.972	0.967	0.634	0.627	0.010	0.030
	R ²	0.452	p < 0.01							
PNL	Std.β	13.368	-0.837	-0.149	-0.175	-0.174	-0.204	-0.201	0.072	0.024
	p	0.001	0.043	0.405	0.298	0.300	0.265	0.271	0.648	0.876
	R ²	0.103	p = 0.043							
USR	Std.β	-19.04	-0.14	0.862	0.105	0.103	0.268	0.270	-0.131	-0.036
	p	0.010	0.161	0.001	0.406	0.414	0.077	0.075	0.122	0.678
	R ²	0.743	p < 0.01							
AUR	Std.β	19.21	0.073	-0.140	-0.334	5.102	0.031	0.014	0.060	0.023
	p	0.001	0.666	0.357	0.035	0.804	0.936	0.972	0.702	0.886
	R ²	0.112	p = 0.035							
UDMR	Std.β	100.275	0.065	-0.407	-26.80	-0.247	0.567	15.508	-0.094	-0.196
	p	0.275	0.746	0.158	0.244	0.572	0.290	0.457	0.566	0.249
	R ²	0.127	p = 0.543							
SOS	Std.β	72.143	-0.937	-1.335	-78.914	2.673	31.374	-2.020	-0.769	0.104
	p	0.050	0.041	0.123	0.164	0.0078	0.609	0.128	0.015	0.712
	R ²	0.683	p = 0.127							
POT	Std.β	8.894	-0.282	-0.425	-3.767	-1.320	-25.812	1.411	-0.021	0.090
	p	0.440	0.513	0.517	0.961	0.282	0.722	0.351	0.946	0.977
	R ²	0.331	p = 0.630							

To evaluate the dynamics of electoral preferences in the 2024 Romanian Parliamentary elections, we performed several regression models considering the electoral scores obtained by parliamentary parties within the electoral process. Thus, we used 7 regression models that have as

dependent variables the electoral scores for the 7 parliamentary parties: 1. ES-PSD; 2. ES-PNL; 3. ES-USR; 4. ES-AUR; 5. ES-UDMR; 6. ES-SOS; 7. ES-POT. Table 5 shows the relevant economic, educational, and demographic factors that predict the dynamics of electoral preferences in the Romanian electoral context.

Empirical findings reveal significant statistical models in the field of electoral preferences for PSD, PNL, AUR, and USR, with significance level $p < 0.05$. In the rest of the cases, the models used for predicting electoral scores of UDMR, S.O.S, and POT, we obtained insignificant statistical values with $p > 0.05$. By these results, we aimed to analyze and discuss only significant statistical models that underline the impact of the economic variables in the field of electoral preferences.

The first regression model predicts the electoral scores of the Social Democratic Party (PSD) with $R^2 = 0.452$, $p < 0.01$. The models highlight that economic variables have a moderate impact on shaping electoral preferences. Thus, the unemployment rate has a significant positive impact on the field of electoral scores related to the social democratic approach ($\beta = 0.497$, $p = 0.001$). These results align with theoretical expectations related to vote behavior, where social democratic parties are more likely to obtain an increased electoral score due to their orientation in the field of social protection and redistributive politics. The model underlines how economically difficult situations are linked with left-wing parties, which are perceived as welfare government actors. This is a classical approach in political science, scholars emphasizing the stabilizing and protective role of left-wing parties for vulnerable groups. This party promises, in all electoral campaigns, redistributive policies, increases in wages and pensions, and the extension of public services in geographical areas characterized by increased unemployment and difficult economic situations. Together with this economic predictor, the model captures the weak positive impact of education ($\beta = 0.3$, $p = 0.01$) and demographic density ($\beta = 0.263$, $p = 0.03$). Figure 2 presents the positive correlation between electoral preferences for the Social Democratic Party (PSD) and unemployment rates in Romanian counties:

Figure 2. Linear regression: unemployment rates and electoral scores of PSD.

The linear regression between unemployment rates and electoral support for PSD shows that in counties with an increased unemployment rate ($UN > 6.00$), the party recorded above-average electoral scores. Counties in Oltenia, South Muntenia, and Moldova are more likely to have a positive relationship between social democratic preferences and higher unemployment rates. In contrast, in counties across Transylvania, Banat, and Crișana, lower unemployment levels are positively related to decreased electoral scores for PSD.

Concerning the regression model explaining the electoral behavior of PNL, statistical results indicate a very weak predictive power with $R^2 = 0.103$, $p = 0.043$. This model suggests a single economic predictor that may explain electoral preferences: contrary to the previous model, the unemployment rate is strongly and negatively related to the electoral scores obtained by PNL in the 2024 parliamentary elections ($\beta = -0.837$, $p=0.043$). In regions with low unemployment rates, citizens might perceive the economic situation as stable. Additionally, the traditional approach of PNL is market-oriented, based on liberal economic policies. Typically, counties with low unemployment levels have higher educational attainment, greater urbanization, and more active private sectors. The regional socio-economic profile could be an important indicator for predicting electoral support for right-wing political parties.

Figure 3. Linear regression: Average Net Salary and electoral support for USR.

The third regression model identifies significant predictors of electoral scores for USR, with $R^2 = 0.743$, $p < 0.01$. Our findings reveal that electoral support for this party is strongly and positively associated with an increased average net salary ($\beta=0.862$, $p=0.001$). USR tends to perform better in regions characterized by economic development and higher personal finances and salaries. As a reformist party, USR advocates for economic reforms, digitalization, and socio-economic alignment with EU values. Its platform resonates with urban, educated, and economically active citizens. Regions with higher GDP levels exhibit stronger demand for modernization, political transparency, economic

development, and anti-corruption policies. Institutional reform and technocratic governance are core themes in the party's rhetoric. However, the party is perceived as a reformist party with liberal values and a right-wing ideological orientation. Electoral support is concentrated among educated groups, many of whom work in the IT industry or the private sector. Political mobilization is closely linked to economic growth and higher average net salaries. Figure 3 shows the linear regression between electoral support for USR and the dynamics of average net salary in 42 Romanian counties.

In connection with these results, we emphasize that counties such as Cluj, Timiș, Bucharest, Sibiu, Ilfov, and Brașov, which are characterized by an increased level of average net salary, report significantly higher electoral support for USR. Additionally, urban areas with high standards of living are more likely to have increased electoral support for the party's platform.

The last regression model reflects, with a weak power of prediction, the interplay between the economy and electoral support for AUR, $R^2=0.112$, $p = 0.035$). In this respect, we estimated a negative association between the level of GDP and electoral support for this party ($\beta = -0.334$, $p = 0.035$). This result suggests that AUR performs better in economically disadvantaged regions, with low levels of GDP and GDP/capita. Several important issues might characterize economically disadvantaged counties, such as limited access to economic opportunities and public services, an increased level of migration, and a strong social and economic cleavage between the center and peripheral areas. In this context, the party has stressed the importance of nationalist discourse, emotional messages, and anti-establishment rhetoric.

The hypothesis of economic vote is demonstrated partially in the 2024 Romanian electoral landscape. A real economic impact in the field of electoral preferences is found in several cases regarding voting for the PSD, PNL, USR, and AUR. In the case of ethnic and populist parties, there are other social, cultural, or political factors that interfere with electoral decisions. Statistical results confirm both the prevalence of the retrospective and sociotropic voters within the Romanian electorate. Limited to the significant statistical models, our theory suggests that economic development functions as an essential mechanism for rewarding and punishing the political class. Results highlight associations between unemployment and left-wing political actors, and average net salary and electoral preferences for right-wing political parties. However, these findings might suggest the classical cleavage between losers and winners of economic transitions in Central and Eastern European countries. Romanian electoral landscape is aligned to these complex realities, revealing an increased level of social and political polarization between vulnerable groups and economically active citizens.

Conclusions

The study presents the nexus between socio-economic variables and electoral behavior in the 2024 Romanian parliamentary elections. Grounded in the theoretical framework of economic voting theory, the paper highlights the main predictors that influenced an increased level of incumbent party reelection and the economic particularities of party preferences. The economic voting theory emphasizes the relevance of both macroeconomic factors and subjective economic perceptions in shaping electoral decisions. However, longitudinal studies in consolidated democracies demonstrated the prevalence of economic voting as a mechanism through which citizens punish or reward governmental performance. Alongside the economic variables, scholars argued that political context, media partisanship, and institutional design are relevant factors that might influence electoral decisions. An important theoretical perspective pointed out the relevance of political information and cognitive heterogeneity in shaping electoral decisions. Informed and sophisticated citizens are more

likely to vote economically than others. In transitional democracies, scholars observed a strong correlation between economic factors and ideological orientation. Left-wing parties are more likely to be correlated with economic imbalances and high unemployment rates. Conversely, right-wing parties are associated with developed regions characterized by an increased level of net salary.

This paper evaluates the impact of economic variables on incumbent party reelection. Using a logistic regression, our findings suggest that the average net salary is more likely to increase the probability of voting for the ruling political party. Together with average net salary, geographical distribution, and level of regional economic development, these factors are involved in shaping electoral behavior in the 2024 Romanian parliamentary elections. Aligned with this finding, we used a multiple linear regression in order to estimate significant predictors of party preferences. Our models have a moderate power of prediction with R^2 between 0.103 and 0.743, revealing that economic voting is relevant only for dominant political parties such as the PSD, PNL, USR, and AUR. Low levels of unemployment are related to liberal preferences. In contrast, vulnerable counties and regions, characterized by increased unemployment rates and a moderate level of economic development, are more likely to be correlated with electoral preferences for PSD. In these regions, statistical data confirms electoral preferences for nationalist discourse promoted by AUR. As regards the developed counties and regions, quantitative results highlight strong positive associations between average net salary and electoral preferences for the reformist approach promoted by USR.

Statistical results are in line with other empirical findings suggesting the relevance of economic development in the field of electoral behavior. Besides economic factors, cultural variables or psychosociological factors predict the dynamics of electoral attitudes and behaviors across counties in the 2024 Romanian parliamentary elections.

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